

HISTORICAL EVOLUTION OF ADDRESSES TO WOMEN IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH

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Abstract. This article aimed to analyze two types of addresses used in social groups for communication: formal and informal. The necessity to comply with official norms, the system of rights and duties and the norms accepted in social groups, and the existence of asymmetrical social relations all influence the type of formal appeal.

Key words: historical-evolutionary, address, Mrs, conversation, language, formal and informal, forms, century, Mistress, non-native English.

Consideration is given to the historical-evolutionary development of the address in both Uzbek and English. This article also discussed the role and importance of the address in other languages based on materials in Uzbek and English. This scientific work reflects the evolution of the address's forms across the language periods under the influence of socio-historical factors. [3]. As certain words become outdated by being replaced with new ones, language can be compared to an aging process. This allows us to assert that language is a dynamic process. Every historical era has its own literary language. However, this does not give us the right to believe that the language of one era is completely distinct from that of another. The process of language change is dynamic; while some language units undergo changes, others remain unchanged and transition into the language of the following era. This demonstrates that language is a two-way process that is complementary to one another: the process by which new words are added to the language and the process by which words become outdated and no longer used in the language. The law of dialectics is this two-step procedure. Synchronous and diachronic approaches play a significant role in the process of language learning. In the examination of forms of address, attention must be given to three important factors: utilization in the current time, historical progression, and dynamic language approach development.

Forms of address are language elements directed to the listener by the speaker, not forming part of the sentence syntactically but adding to the overall meaning of the sentence. Assisted by them, we can initiate, carry on, and conclude discussions effectively. For example:

– In order to start the conversation: *“How are you, my dear? said Laura cheerfully, putting aside the paper”, “Xush ko‘rdik xonim! – dedi-da unga o‘ng yelkasini tutdi”*

– in order to continue the conversation: *“Quarrel, Madam! no, mam”; “E, so‘ramang, egachi...”*;

– in order to finish the conversation successfully: *“Come, Miss, let’s away”; “Undoq bo‘lsa menga javob bering Malikam! –dedi Qutlug‘ Nigorxonim” [5].*

While talking about the role of the forms of address, first of all, it is worth mentioning that in the sentence of English and Uzbek language, they are separated with the comma or they come with exclamation marks after it for the purpose to show the strong emotion of the speaker: – *“Quarrel, Madam! no, mam”!* [3]; – *Bizni kechirasiz oya! – deb Nigora uzr aytdi*). They also express the social background, age, gender, profession, state of the speaker, the register of the conversation, and the attitude of the speakers towards each other. For example, in the following sentence *“Good morning, Mrs. Brown”*, with the help of the form of address Mrs. we understand that the conversation is formal, listener is an educated woman and there is a positive attitude of the speaker towards the listener.

As previously noted, the development of the forms of address is significantly influenced by social and historical factors. The three periods are known to be followed in the study of the English language's development:

1) The Old English language, 2) the Middle English language, 3) the New English language. The ancient English language includes the period approximately between VII century and 1100. In that period of the English language we can notice the wide use of forms of address.

In the function of the forms of address in the sentence, the aforementioned examples show a broad use of relative and adjectival phrases to convey emotion. The conquest of Scandinavia and Norway, which brought the Scandinavian dialect and later the French language to English-speaking people, is linked to the development of the Middle English language. The Norman conquest holds a significant place in English history because, at that time, English became an official language and was widely utilized by government officials and artists, while ordinary people used English in their daily lives. The English language became the official language of the country at the end of the Norman era in England, although there had been significant changes in the vocabulary of the English language by then. Some of the English-language address forms, such as *mōdor-mōðer* (mother), show Scandinavian influence [2]. Some new words that conveyed the forms of salutation entered the English language as a result of the Norman Conquest:

princess, baroness, duchess, and others [6]. At this point in the history of the English language, the forms of address were regarded as active linguistic units: Herkneht to me, gode woman, wiues, maydnes, and alle woman, pat ich yu telle=Eshitinglar meni, men sizlarga hikoya so‘zlay, azizlarim, qadrdon opa-singillarim, va barchalaringiz [6]; From 1500 until the present, the following period is known as the New English Language Period. This era includes the years between the XV and XXI centuries. Numerous changes were made to the companies' addresses during this time. For instance, in the 19th century, phrases and names of relation (father, mother) were used to address people, and titles like saint, lady, master, man (men), and woman (women) became used. Throughout the sixteenth century, "emotional nouns" were frequently used as forms of address (daddy, mammy) in families, in addition to forms of address associated with "age" (child, girl, dally, young), short forms of terms expressing relation (chez, pa, ma), forms used to address people of higher social class (MY Honour, Highness, Duke, Lord, Lordship, Lady, Sir, Master, His/Her Excellency), and forms of address consisting of name+surname due to their widespread usage in the language. An example might be: "This is a Montague, your foe, Aunt" [4].

In the XVII century, we can notice other words being used as the forms of address. In this period forms like *Mrs=Missis* surname, words expressing respect *Ma'am, Missis, businesswoman*, words expressing profession *doctor, soldiers, priest and physician* were becoming popular as the forms of address among people: *Horner. No, good Domineer Doctor, I tricked you it seems, and others too* [3]. We do not notice any big changes in the usage of the forms of address in the XVIII century. During this century addressing people using their name + surname, or using the short forms of their names or surnames with adjectives (dear, honest, hunny, love) and *Mrs= Mistress + name* became widespread in communication: **Hard Mrs. Marlow – Mrs. Hastings – young lady – pray be under no constraint in this house.** [3].

In the XIX century the forms of address became simple and easy to use. Using name + surname with the words expressing respect *Mrs. + surname* and *Mrs.* with other were the forms of address specific to this century.

Alice! I think that is rather mean of you, Joanna.

Julia. Did you tell him Mrs. Worthington was in town?

Lucy. Yes, Mam.

Addressing occurs so frequently in social interactions that it is a crucial component of communication. The basic idea is that one cannot expect the target language to have the same effect as his native tongue when the identical

expressions are translated literally into another language. However, for foreign language learners, it appears that interference from another person's language is unavoidable in practice. In social interactions, address phenomena are both frequent and significant. Appropriate address behavior is essential for successful interpersonal relationship maintenance and effective communication. Typically, the culturally bound politeness phenomenon governs address behavior. Misunderstandings and misinterpretations can cause the people involved to feel offended, insulted, and suspicious, which will lead to a breakdown in cross-cultural communication. For example, non-native English speakers frequently express astonishment at the widespread usage or distribution of recitational first names among Americans and British citizens. The forms of address in Uzbek language are also considered as one of the important language unities as in English language. In Uzbek language the forms of address are studied in conjunction with their historical development.

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